

CURRENT STATE OF CUSTOMS PAYMENTS ACCOUNTING ORGANIZATION AND PROSPECTS FOR ITS DEVELOPMENT

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"Customs payments play a significant role in ensuring sustainable development of the national economy by regulating external trade flows to a necessary degree, and are used to achieve economic security, as well as fiscal objectives.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Strategy of Uzbekistan-2030" has been adopted. According to this Decree, one of the priority directions is identified as "Ensuring prosperity of the population through sustainable economic growth". The objective outlined under this direction in goal number 46, titled "Ensuring consolidation of budget sustainability by reducing the share of consolidated budget deficit relative to GDP from 4% in 2024 to 3% in subsequent years", has been specified." [1]

"Managing customs payments remains a pressing issue in today's context. Customs payments are managed through the Customs Cargo Declaration (CCD), which serves as the basis for operations. One critical aspect in formalizing customs declarations is the conversion of contracts denominated in various foreign currencies to the national currency, the som, for the calculation of customs payments.

These issues are addressed under the budget accounting standard "Impact of Exchange Rate Changes" (No. 4 in the BPS). It stipulates that for budget accounting, the value of assets and liabilities utilized in foreign currencies must be recalculated into som for reporting purposes. The official exchange rate on the date when transactions in foreign currencies occurred is used for this purpose [2].

The value of imported goods and associated liabilities in foreign currency are reassessed on the last working day of the reporting period based on the official exchange rate on the date of the transaction in foreign currency.

Under item 45 of the Customs Cargo Declaration, the customs value recorded in the contract currency is converted into som for customs payment calculation purposes, based on item 47 of the CCD. Therefore, to calculate the

customs value, it is necessary to multiply the customs value (item 45) by the contract currency exchange rate (item 23) as stated in item 47.

Customs payments are calculated and levied in the national currency, the som.

Next, we examine the specific characteristics of accounts and accounting balances of business entities engaged in importing. In the company's accounting department, the specifics of customs payments are recorded as follows (Table 1). Customs payment benefits received are reflected as credits in account '8840 - Special Tax Benefits Utilized'. This amount is recorded under the financial reporting form 'Accounting Balance', in the liabilities section 'Special Levies' at line 460."[2]

1-table.

Double-entry accounting entries accounting for concessions from customs payments at importing enterprises

T/p	Content of economic transactions	Value (mill.som)	Accounting records	
			Debit	Kredit
1	In the importing enterprise, accounting entries were made for the exemption from customs payments	100,0	1010 - "raw materials and materials" [3]	6991 - "creditor's debt for received inventory - current part"
2	Exemptions from customs payments on imported goods were reflected.	100,0	6991 - "creditor's debt on the received inventory - current part"	8840 - "purposeful tax credits"

"As shown in the table, importers add the customs duty exemption to the value of imported goods. When there are exemptions related to customs duties, it is necessary to provide information regarding the regulatory documents that stipulate the exemption from customs duties according to the requirements in box 44 of the Customs Declaration.

In this case, detailing the mutual connection of accounting accounts used by budget agencies and importers for the calculation and payment of customs

duties can facilitate clarification of the issue and enable acceptance of appropriate management decisions (Table 2)."

2-table.

Comparative analysis of accounting transfers used by budgetary authorities and importers for the calculation and payment of customs duties

Contents of operations on customs payments	Calculation of customs fees in importers		Calculation of customs fees at the customs authority	
	Debit	Kredit	Debit	Kredit
Debts to the budget for various deductions, taxes and fees related to period expenses	9430	6410		
The amount of VAT and excise duty was calculated on the sale of finished products, goods, performance of work and provision of services, as well as the sale of fixed assets and other assets and various issues	4010	6410		
The amount of VAT related to material resources, goods, works and services was taken into account	6410	4410		
Debts to the budget were paid from the received loans and debts	6410	6810-6840, 7810-7840		
Funds received in the single treasury account were accepted to the relevant revenues of the budgets of the budget system (in the appropriate branch of the treasury departments)			102 417	140 000
Tax and customs revenues were returned based on the			140000	102 417

conclusion of the authorized body and relevant documents in the treasury departments (according to the relevant budgets).				
In the treasury departments (according to the relevant budgets), an amendment was made to the reference books of the tax authorities, based on the income calculated on the tax and customs payments of the previous fiscal year.			141 000	991 100
Cancellation or reduction of income obligation calculated in previous years			991 100	141 000

Based on the analysis above, we can come to the following conclusions:

1. Analyzing the uniqueness of the codes and names of accounts in the budget sector and production sectors of the economy will complicate the identification of analytical conclusions.

2. The need to adhere to the conceptual foundations and procedures of accounting accounts according to international standards is confirmed, and the benefits of using economic concepts and accounting procedures in various economic sectors and areas are emphasized.

Considering the implementation of public leadership in accounting for the economy and finance ministry, organizing and finalizing the accounting for customs duties, as well as streamlining, automating financial and accounting processes, identifying financial reporting forms, transforming them according to international standards, "University 4.0" requires integration of education, production, and trade processes.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Decree No. PF-158 of September 11, 2023 "On the strategy of "Uzbekistan - 2030". <https://lex.uz/docs/6600413>.

2. The standard of budget accounting of the Republic of Uzbekistan(SBA No.4) "Effect of exchange rate changes" : www.lex.uz.

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3. National accounting standard of the Republic of Uzbekistan NAS No. 21.

4. www.lex.uz.

